

METHOD ARTICLE

Oriented artificial nanofibers and laser induced periodic surface structures as substrates for Schwann cells alignment

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Sebastian Lifka ¹, Cristina Plamadeala², Agnes Weth¹, Johannes Heitz², Werner Baumgartner¹

¹Institute of Biomedical Mechatronics, Johannes Kepler University Linz, Linz, Upper Austria, 4040, Austria

²Institute of Applied Physics, Johannes Kepler University Linz, Linz, Upper Austria, 4040, Austria

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Abstract

People with injuries to the peripheral nervous system, due to its poor functional regeneration, suffer from paralysis of the facial muscles, fingers and hands, or toes and feet, often for the rest of their lives. Therefore, to improve patients' quality of life, there is an urgent need for conduits that effectively support the healing of large defects in nerve pathways through specific guidance of nerve cells. This paper describes two specific methods for achieving directed growth of Schwann cells, a type of glial cells that can support the regeneration of the nerve pathway by guiding the neuronal axons in the direction of their alignment. One method implies the exposure of a poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) foil to a KrF* laser beam, that renders a nanorippled surface topography. The other method uses aligned polyamide-6 (PA-6) nanofibers produced via electrospinning on a very fast rotating structured collector, which enables easy nanofiber detachment, without additional effort. Schwann cells growth on these substrates was inspected after one week of cultivation by means of scanning electron microscope (SEM). For both methods we show that Schwann cells grow in a certain direction, predetermined by nanoripples and nanofibers orientation. In contrast, cells cultivated onto unstructured surfaces or randomly oriented nanofibers, show an omnidirectional growth behavior.

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1. **Harald Luksch** , Technische Universität München, Weihenstephan, Germany
2. **Sandra I. Vieira**, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal
Nathalie Barroca, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal
3. **Tak-Ho Chu** , University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

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Aligned Nanofibers, Electrospinning, Nanoripples, Laser-Induced Periodic Surface Structures, Nerve Regeneration, Tissue Engineering, Schwann cells

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Corresponding authors: Sebastian Lifka (sebastian.lifka@jku.at), Cristina Plamadeala (cristina.plamadeala@jku.at)

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Introduction

One possibility to guide Schwann cells would be the use of natural silk. (Millesi *et al.*, 2021) and (Stadlmayr *et al.*, 2024), for example, have recently conducted promising research into the use of natural spider silk in nerve regeneration. Since the harvesting of natural silk can be costly and time-consuming, the use of artificial fibers, such as nanofibers produced using the so-called electrospinning process, would be advantageous. Several processes for the production of aligned nanofibers using electrospinning have already been described in the literature (Han *et al.*, 2022). Directed nanofibers have also been used as scaffolds in nerve regeneration. (Huang *et al.*, 2015) used directed cellulose acetate butyrate (CAB) nanofibers for the regeneration of nerves in rats.

A second possibility to guide Schwann cells is to create a substrate with nanoripples, also known as laser-induced periodic surface structures (LIPSS), that can be achieved by short-pulsed laser processing (Bonse *et al.*, 2017). (Rebollar *et al.*, 2008) showed that nanoripples on polystyrene (PS) enable directed growth of Chinese hamster ovary (CHO) cells proving that nano topography similar to the nanofeatures found in the extracellular matrix (ECM) provides an important external stimulus and induce an orientation of actin fibers of the cytoskeleton. It has been also demonstrated that laser-induced topography in combination with shear stress affect the adhesion, orientation and elongation of mouse Schwann cells (Babaliari *et al.*, 2021).

In this work we present two methods which can be used effectively in the future for the production of implants in nerve regeneration. The first method enables the production of aligned nanofibers which can be easily detached from the electrospinning collector as an independent non-woven without additional coating or complex additional work, as it was the case up to now and thus significantly simplifies the manufacturing process. This is achieved by a collector rotating at a very high speed which winds up the electrospun fiber as if on a wire drum. The surface of the collector is structured with a special micro-surface structure, which has already been described in more detail in a previous publication (Lifka *et al.*, 2023). The surface structure allows the nanofiber non-woven to be removed from the collector easily and without leaving any residue. The second method describes the production of laser-induced periodic surface structures (LIPSS), also known as nanoripples, which, due to their resemblance to the ECM, enable the aligned growth of nerve cells. For both methods we show that, in contrast to randomly oriented fibers or unstructured surfaces, they promote oriented cell growth in a direction predefined by the orientation of the fibers and ripples.

Methods

Aligned nanofibers

The most important and novel part of this method is the rotating collector whose surface contains a structure in the μm range. This structure has already been presented in a previous publication and consists in principle of a simple triangular geometry which forms a jagged surface structure. In (Lifka *et al.*, 2023), this structure was produced on a cylindrical

collector with the aid of a thread turning tool in the form of a very fine thread, whereby the direction of preference of the structure is orthogonal to the collector axis. This variant represents the most unfavorable alignment of the structure for this application (the aligned nanofibers must be orthogonal to the direction of the structure in order to guarantee its function). Therefore, the structure must be manufactured in such a way that its orientation is parallel to the cylinder/collector axis. In the sense of simple, fast and cost-effective production, the triangular structure was produced by knurling the cylinder surface with axis-parallel grooves.

For this purpose, a cylindrical collector made of aluminum with a diameter of 40 mm was manufactured and machined on a lathe using a knurling wheel (ZEUS knurling wheel 11 AA 15 x 4 x 4 G7 T=0.3 PM a=90°, Article number: 41013392, Hommel+Keller Präzisionswerkzeuge GmbH, Aldingen, Germany) with the triangular surface structure. The structure therefore has a periodicity and depth of approximately 300 μm with a tip angle of 90°. To enable the collector to rotate, it is supported by two ball bearings (6001-2Z, SKF Österreich AG, Steyr, Austria) to the left and right of the structured surface. The bearing blocks were manufactured using a 3D printer (Photon Mono-X, Hongkong Anycubic Technology Co., Shenzhen, China). The resin used for the 3D printed parts was the “Blu” resin from Siraya Tech (Blu-Tough Resin/Nylon Black, Siraya Tech, San Gabriel, California, USA). The collector is driven by a brushless DC motor (DB28M01, Nanotec Electronic GmbH & Co. KG, Feldkirchen, Germany) via a claw coupling (MJC19-4-A, JD12/19-85B; Ruland Manufacturing Co., Inc., Marlborough, UK). The maximum achievable rotational speed of the collector is approximately 14 meter per second. All CAD data and 2D drawing derivation required for the production of the collector are freely available in a Zenodo repository (Lifka *et al.*, 2024).

For electrospinning, the rotating drum collector assembly (Figure 1B) was mounted on a custom-made electrospinning setup, as shown in Figure 1A. The setup is based on the classic horizontal electrospinning process in which a polymer solution is conveyed evenly through a thin metal needle with the aid of a syringe pump and applied to a collector in the form of thin nanofibers with the use of a strong electric field. The setup consists of a basic frame made of aluminum profiles which enables precise adjustment of the needle-collector distance. The polymer solution is conveyed evenly through a thin metal needle (Sterican 21G x 7/8" blunt, B. Braun SE, Melsungen, Germany) using a custom-made syringe pump. The necessary electric field is generated by a high-voltage generator (HCP 35-35,000, FuG Elektronik GmbH, Schechen, Germany). The needle is the positive electrode and the collector is the negative electrode. The needle is contacted directly via a crocodile clip, while the collector is contacted via the conductive ball bearings to avoid sliding contact. The polymer solution for the nanofibers consists of 15 wt.% polyamide-6 (PA6) (provided by Elmarco s.r.o., Liberec, Czech Republic) dissolved in formic acid (FA) (ROTIPURAN® $\geq 98\%$, p.a., ACS, Art. No. 4724.1, Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG., Karlsruhe, Germany), and acetic acid (AA)

Figure 1. Electrospinning-setup for the production of aligned nanofibers. (A) Custom-made electrospinning setup. (B) Rotating drum collector setup mounted on the electrospinning setup-

(ROTIPURAN 100%, p.a., Art. No. 3738.4, Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG., Karlsruhe, Germany) in a (weight) ratio of 2:1. A total of 15 g of the polymer solution was prepared, for which 2.25 g PA6, 4.25 g FA and 8.5 g AA were used. The parameters for the spinning process were selected as follows: Needle-collector distance of 13 cm, needle-collector voltage of 20 kV, and flow rate of 0.34 mLh^{-1} .

The motor speed was controlled and set via the software “Plug & Drive Studio 3” (v. 1.5.3.0, Nanotec Electronic GmbH & Co. KG, Feldkirchen, Germany). Various rotational speeds of the collector were tested until the fibers were oriented in the desired direction. The electrospinning process took about 10 minutes for each sample. After this time, a fleece that was thick and robust enough for further processing could be guaranteed. The finished non-woven was then cut open with a scalpel parallel to the collector axis and carefully removed from the collector with tweezers. Thanks to the surface structuring, the fleece could be removed easily and without leaving any residue. The Zenodo repository (Lifka *et al.*, 2024) contains a video (Non-Woven_Detachment_from_Collector.mkv) showing the removal process of the aligned nanofiber non-woven. The specimens of the nanofiber non-woven were then sputter-coated with gold (SCD 005, BAL-TEC Inc., Balzers, Liechtenstein) for 80 s with 21 mA and examined under a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Philips 525, Philips

Electron Optics, Amsterdam, The Netherlands). The SEM images subsequently serve as the basis for the analysis of the directionality and the average fiber diameter.

The statistical analyses of fiber directionality and fiber diameter were performed using *ImageJ* (v. 1.51w, Rasband, W.S., U. S. National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, Maryland, USA). The directionality analysis function (v2.3.0, method: Fourier components) was used to analyze the fiber orientation. The DiameterJ (v. 1-018) plug-in (Hotaling *et al.*, 2015) was used to analyze the fiber diameter. The corresponding diagrams were created with the help of *Python-3* (v. 3.10.9, Python Software Foundation, Beaverton, Oregon, USA) and *matplotlib* (v. 3.3) (Hunter, 2007) from the .csv files generated by *ImageJ*. All underlying data can be found in the Zenodo repository (Lifka *et al.*, 2024).

Nanoripples

To produce ripples on poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) foils with a thickness of $50 \mu\text{m}$ (Goodfellow Ltd., Bad Nauheim, Germany), a KrF* (krypton fluoride) excimer laser (LPX 300, Lambda Physik, 181 Göttingen, Germany) was used, with a wavelength of 248 nm, 20 ns pulse duration, and 10 Hz pulse repetition rate. The setup is similar to the setup for laser processing of PET foils used in (Richter *et al.*, 2021) and is shown in Figure 2. Prior to exposure, the PET foils were rinsed with

Figure 2. Setup for laser-induced periodic surface structures (LIPSS) fabrication on poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) foils. (Reprinted from (Buchberger *et al.*, 2023) which is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International \(CC-BY 4.0\)](#)).

ethanol and thoroughly dried with nitrogen, in order to remove any debris. Later on, the foils were fixed onto the sample holder at a 30° incidence angle and exposed to 6000 pulses at an energy of 12.6 – 12.8 mJ, applying an average fluence of 10 mJ cm⁻². Laser beam energy was measured with a high-area high-damage energy sensor (J45LP-MUV, Coherent, Portland, United States) with the help of a laser energy meter (FieldMaxII-P™, Coherent, Portland, USA).

Scanning electron microscope (model REM 1540XB-Crossbeam, Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany) images of nanoripples were acquired at ten different positions within the nanostructured area and analyzed by using the free software [Gwyddion](#) (v. 2.61, Czech Metrology Institute, Brno, Czech Republic) in order to calculate the spatial period. The underlying data for spatial period calculation “Spatial period calculation.docx” can be found in the Zenodo repository (Lifka *et al.*, 2024).

Cell cultivation

To validate and show the oriented cell growth on samples produced with the above described methods, murine Schwann cells (Immortalized Mouse Schwann Cells (IMS32), T0295, Applied Biological Materials Inc., Richmond, Canada) were cultured for ten days in 4 mL grow medium consisting of PriGrow III (TM003, Applied Biological Materials Inc., Richmond, Canada) + 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS)(F7524, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Lois, Missouri, USA) + 1% Penicillin/Streptomycin Solution (G255, Applied Biological Materials Inc., Richmond, Canada) at 37.0 °C and 5% CO₂ in an incubator (New Brunswick Galaxy® 48 S CO₂, Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany) on the corresponding sample. The medium was changed every

two days. Prior to cell cultivation, samples were coated with a poly-L-lysine hydrobromide (P9155, Sigma Aldrich, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Lois, Missouri, USA) solution at a concentration of 40 µg ml⁻¹ in double-distilled water, incubated for 10 minutes at room temperature, then washed with distilled water, and finally air-dried at room temperature.

Image manipulation

All images shown in the figures have been slightly manipulated to improve the clarity of the figures. The original, unmanipulated images can be found as underlying data in the Zenodo repository (Lifka *et al.*, 2024). The software used for image manipulation was on the one hand [Corel Vector](#) (v. 23.0.0.363, Alludo, Ottawa, Canada) and on the other hand [Inkscape](#) (v. 0.92.4, The Inkscape Project c/o Software Freedom Conservancy, Brooklyn, New York, USA). While Corel Vector is a proprietary software, Inkscape is a freely available software that performs essentially the same functions. All image manipulations are listed in detail below:

- In [Figure 1](#) the images “Figure 1A_original.jpg” and “Figure 1B_original.jpg” from the Zenodo repository were merged, labeled, and annotated in one Figure using Inkscape.
- In [Figure 3](#) three single frames of the video “Non-Woven_Detachment_from_Collector.mkv” in the Zenodo repository were captured using the [VLC media player](#) (v. 3.0.20, VideoLan Organization, Paris, France), merged into one figure, labeled, and annotated using Inkscape.

- In **Figure 4** the images “Figure 4A_original.tif”, “Figure 4B_original.tif”, “Figure 4C_original.tif”, and “Figure 4D_original.tif” from the Zenodo repository were merged, cropped, labeled, and annotated in one Figure using Inkscape.
- In **Figure 6** the images “Figure 6A_original.tif” and “Figure 6B_original.tif” from the Zenodo repository were merged, labeled, and annotated in one Figure using Corel Vector.
- In **Figure 7** the images “Figure 7A_original.tif”, “Figure 7B_original.tif”, and “Figure 7CD_original.tif” from the Zenodo repository were merged, cropped, labeled, and annotated in one Figure using Corel Vector. **Figure 7D** is a zoomed version of **Figure 7C**.
- In the Figure S1 embedded in the underlying data “Spatial period calculation.docx” the image “Figure S1A_original.tif” from the Zenodo repository was labeled and annotated using Corel Vector.

Results

Aligned nanofibers

Figure 3A to C show an example of the detachment process for the nanofiber non-woven. It can be seen that the non-woven

can be removed easily and without leaving any residue on the collector. The video “Non-Woven_Detachement_from_Collector.mkv” in the Zenodo repository ([Lifka et al., 2024](#)) shows the removal process again in detail.

Figure 4 shows the SEM images of four different nanofiber non-woven. **Figure 4A** shows a non-woven with randomly oriented fibers (i.e. the collector did not rotate) as a control. **Figure 4B to C** show non-woven with increasing collector rotation speed. It can be clearly seen that the degree of orientation of the fibers increases with the rotational speed of the collector. While the orientation of the fibers still has potential for improvement at a rotational speed of $v = 5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ (**Figure 4B**), a clear orientation in the horizontal direction can already be seen at a rotational speed of $v = 8 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ or $v = 14 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ (**Figure 4C and D**).

To better quantify the directionality of the fibers, **Figure 5** shows the directionality histograms for all SEM images of **Figure 4**. The horizontal line in the histogram represents an angle of 0° . The dashed curve in red represents a normal distribution fit. It can be clearly seen that the sample with the randomly oriented fibers (**Figure 5A**) is relatively evenly distributed in all directions. The sample with $v = 5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ (**Figure 5B**) is much more directional in comparison. The samples in which the collector was rotated at $v = 8 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ (**Figure 5C**) and $v = 14 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ (**Figure 5D**) both exhibit excellent directionality.

Figure 3. Removal process of the oriented nanofiber non-woven. (A) Cut open the fleece with a scalpel. (B) Remove the fleece with tweezers. (C) Fleece completely detached from the collector without leaving any residue on the collector.

Figure 4. SEM images of the aligned nanofiber non-woven. (A) Randomly oriented nanofibers as control (i.e., the collector did not rotate, $v = 0 \text{ ms}^{-1}$). (B) Nanofibers collected on the collector rotating with $v = 5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$. (C) Nanofibers collected on the collector rotating with $v = 8 \text{ ms}^{-1}$. (D) Nanofibers collected on the collector rotating with $v = 14 \text{ ms}^{-1}$.

Figure 5. Directionality histograms of the non-woven. (A) Randomly oriented nanofibers as control (i.e., the collector did not rotate, $v = 0 \text{ ms}^{-1}$). (B) Nanofibers collected on the collector rotating with $v = 5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$. (C) Nanofibers collected on the collector rotating with $v = 8 \text{ ms}^{-1}$. (D) Nanofibers collected on the collector rotating with $v = 14 \text{ ms}^{-1}$. The dashed red line represents a normal distribution fit of the histogram.

Table 1 lists the average fiber diameters of the individual samples. On average across all samples, the fibers produced had a diameter of approx. 250 nm with a standard deviation of approximately 110 nm.

To investigate the directional cell growth on the samples, murine Schwann cells were cultured on an 8 ms^{-1} non-woven nanofiber sample (**Figure 4C**), which has a parallel fiber direction (**Figure 5C**). The result can be seen in **Figure 6A**. A clear orientation of the cell growth in a horizontal direction can be seen. **Figure 6B** shows an enlarged section of **Figure 6A**, in which the non-woven under the cells is also visible. Note that the orientation of the nanofibers is also horizontal (i.e., parallel to the direction of cell growth).

Nanoripples

Nanoripples (LIPSS) are structures that form upon laser irradiation on many materials, and originate from the interference of the incoming linearly polarized light of (ultra-)short pulsed

lasers with the radiation remnants or plasmon modes in the surface (**Bonse et al., 2017**). The orientation of the LIPSS can be either parallel or perpendicular to the polarization of the laser beam and their periodicity is comparable to the wavelength or smaller, depending on the laser fluence and the angle of incidence of the laser beam onto the irradiated substrate. In our case, the spatial period Λ of nanoripples fabricated using s-polarized laser light is given by $\Lambda = \lambda / (n_{\text{eff}} - \sin\theta)$, where λ is the wavelength of the laser beam, n_{eff} – the effective refractive index which lies between the refractive indices of air and PET (**Barb et al., 2014**), and θ – the angle of incidence.

Figure 7A shows the murine Schwann cells cultivated for one week (same procedure as described above) on flat PET foil, used as reference sample. The cells show a random orientation and omnidirectional growth. In contrast, **Figure 7B**, showing murine Schwann cells cultivated for one week on PET nanoripples, proves the influence of nanorippled topography as external stimuli that renders cell alignment. Schwann cells exhibit a typical elongated bipolar shape and even though their sizes (in the order of some tens of micrometers) are much bigger than the nanoripples' height (above 110 nm (**Buchberger et al., 2023**)) and periodicity ($\Lambda = 331 \pm 11 \text{ nm}$, $N = 10$), the cells align and orient themselves along the LIPSS orientation. This effect happens due to the interaction of cell filopodia with the nano topography, as shown in **Figure 7C and D**.

Discussion

In this work, two methods are described to present an improved directed growth of Schwann cells, a type of glial cell that insulates and protects the axons of neurons. Major injuries of nerve tissue are often characterized by poor functional regeneration and therefore require conduits that promote healing of the nerve axons and provide direction for Schwann cell growth.

Table 1. Mean fiber diameters of the samples.

	Mean fiber diameter in nm	Standard deviation in nm
Random oriented	277.5	110.4
5 ms^{-1}	205.9	81.3
8 ms^{-1}	226.5	101.4
14 ms^{-1}	309.0	151.5
Overall	254.725	111.15

Figure 6. SEM images of aligned murine Schwann cells cultivated for one week on electrospun PA-6 nanofibers with preferential orientation. (B) is a magnified detail of (A), where the underlying nearly parallel oriented nanofibers are better visible. The nanofiber sample was spun with a rotational collector speed of 8 ms^{-1} as shown in **Figure 4C.**

Figure 7. Murine Schwann cells on PET foils. (A) SEM image of murine Schwann cells cultivated for one week on flat PET foil, as control, showing no alignment. (B–D) SEM images of aligned murine Schwann cells cultivated for one week on a PET foil with nanoripples. (C, D) are magnifications of (B), showing an area with incomplete cell coverage, proving that the cells and the nanoripples have the same orientation.

One method uses laser-induced periodic surface structures (LIPSS) that mimic the nanofeatures found in the extracellular matrix. These LIPSS can be used to specify the direction of growth for Schwann cells and promote growth in a specific direction. However, this is limited to more or less rigid (in this case) PET films. Therefore, a second method describes the production of a non-woven consisting of nanofibers. This non-woven is extremely flexible and can be adapted to many different shapes. The method is based on the electrospinning process and uses a very fast rotating cylindrical collector to produce directed nanofibers. The special feature of the method is the special surface structure (Lifka *et al.*, 2023) of the collector, which enables the non-woven to be easily removed without additional coating and additional effort. In this work, only one fiber material was tested, namely PA-6, as good experience has already been made with this polymer. Of course, this method can also be applied to biocompatible polymers, such as fibers made of cellulose acetate butyrate (CAB) or collagen fibers. These materials would be very well suited for use in nerve regeneration.

Conclusion

In this paper we show that oriented mechanical nanofeatures, such as nanofibers and nanoripples, are able to mimic the extracellular matrix features, and stimulate the elongation and

support the alignment of Schwann cells. These attributes may subsequently lead to a better axonal regeneration.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Data and software availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: Repository for the Method Article “Oriented artificial nanofibers and laser induced periodic surface structures as substrates for Schwann cells alignment”. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10665996> (Lifka *et al.*, 2024).

This project contains the following underlying data:

- Directionality_Hist.py. (Python file for generating directionality histograms of the non-woven.)
- RandomHist.csv. (Histogram data from ImageJ for random oriented non-woven.)
- 5mpsHist.csv. (Histogram data from ImageJ for 5 ms⁻¹ non-woven.)
- 8mpsHist.csv. (Histogram data from ImageJ for 8 ms⁻¹ non-woven.)

- 14mpsHist.csv. (Histogram data from ImageJ for 14 ms⁻¹ non-woven.)
- DiameterAnalysisRandom.csv. (Fiber diameter analysis and histogram data from ImageJ for random oriented non-woven.)
- DiameterAnalysis5mps.csv. (Fiber diameter analysis and histogram data from ImageJ for 5 ms⁻¹ non-woven.)
- DiameterAnalysis8mps.csv. (Fiber diameter analysis and histogram data from ImageJ for 8 ms⁻¹ non-woven.)
- DiameterAnalysis14mps.csv. (Fiber diameter analysis and histogram data from ImageJ for 14 ms⁻¹ non-woven.)
- Spatial period calculation.docx. (Word file containing the data for the spatial period calculation of the nanoripples.)
- Figure 1A_original.jpg. (Original unmanipulated image used for Figure 1A.)
- Figure 1B_original.jpg. (Original unmanipulated image used for Figure 1B.)
- Figure 4A_original.tif. (Original unmanipulated image used for Figure 4A.)
- Figure 4B_original.tif. (Original unmanipulated image used for Figure 4B.)
- Figure 4C_original.tif. (Original unmanipulated image used for Figure 4C.)
- Figure 4D_original.tif. (Original unmanipulated image used for Figure 4D.)
- Figure 6A_original.tif. (Original unmanipulated image used for Figure 6A.)
- Figure 6B_original.tif. (Original unmanipulated image used for Figure 6B.)
- Figure 7A_original.tif. (Original unmanipulated image used for Figure 7A.)
- Figure 7B_original.tif. (Original unmanipulated image used for Figure 7B.)
- Figure 7CD_original.tif. (Original unmanipulated image used for Figure 7C and D.) Figure S1A_original.tif. (Original unmanipulated image used for Figure S1A.)

Extended data

Zenodo: Repository for the Method Article “Oriented artificial nanofibers and laser induced periodic surface structures as substrates for Schwann cells alignment”. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10665996> (Lifka *et al.*, 2024).

This project contains the following extended data:

- Bearing bracket Fixed bearing.step. (CAD .step file for the fixed bearing bracket of the rotating drum collector setup.)
- Bearing bracket loose fit bearing.step. (CAD .step file for the loose bearing bracket of the rotating drum collector setup.)
- Bearing cover Fixed bearing.step. (CAD .step file for the fixed bearing cover of the rotating drum collector setup.)
- Bearing cover loose fit bearing.step. (CAD .step file for the loose bearing cover of the rotating drum collector setup.)
- Motor mount.step. (CAD .step file for the DC motor mount of the rotating drum collector setup.)
- Surface structured collector.step. (CAD .step file for the surface-structured rotating drum collector.)
- Surface Structured Collector Drawing.pdf. (2D drawing of the rotating drum collector.)
- Setup Rotating Collector.pdf. (2D drawing of the whole rotating drum collector setup.)
- Non-Woven_Detachment_from_Collector.mkv (Short video showing the detachment process of the non-woven fabric from the surface-structured collector.)

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) (CC-BY 4.0).

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Sandra I. Vieira

Institute of Biomedicine (iBiMED) research unit - Department of Medical Sciences, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

Nathalie Barroca

TEMA research unit - Department of Mechanic Engineering, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

Lifka et al. here present two methods for structuring surfaces aiming to improve the alignment of cells like Schwann cells, important for aiding the oriented growth of neuronal axons during peripheral nervous system regeneration. The methods are generally sound and the Zenodo repository associated with this article has examples of various of the steps taken and calculations performed. The authors cultured mouse Schwann cells for one week on top of the aligned nanofibers and PET nanoripples, which appear to have induced cell alignment. It is particularly visible the influence of the nanorippled topography as an external stimulus that renders the Schwann cells' alignment.

The Introduction section has some relevant reported data, but nothing on the biological problem that authors aim to tackle, which should not only be addressed in the Abstract (attention that PNI regeneration is not that ineffective – only in 'large defects'). To better contextualize the need for the here-developed biomaterials, authors should include a short characterization of the PNS regeneration process, including the role of Schwann cells in bands of Bungner, in the Introduction section. This is necessary to support the author's Conclusion that the alignment of Schwann cells may subsequently lead to better axonal regeneration. As for the manufacturing technologies, the introduction should also contextualize better the current state of the art regarding the exploitation of electrospinning and LIPSS, to highlight their relevance for repairing strategies for the PNS. For instance, the direct laser patterning technique has been already used to fabricate nanoripples and dual-rough hierarchical micro/nano structures to control Schwann cells attachment and migration. [Refer ref 1].

Also, since nano-structuring is known for both boosting and inhibiting cell functions, this should be carefully explained in the introduction.

One of the methods here described applied electrospinning to create aligned polyamide nanofibers, in which a fast-rotating structured collector with a knurled surface is used, to allow the nanofibers to be effectively peeled off. Regarding the cellular alignment assay, one thing noticed is that the nanofibers of Figure 6B augmentation do not seem aligned, and authors should present a more representative zoom-in. Also, no control such as randomly aligned nanofibers, was here included for comparison purposes, and so the readers cannot visually certify the cell alignment effect. As this biomaterial is the core of this article, it would also be desirable to a) apply the same strategy as the one used in Figure 5 to have some quantitative data on cell alignment; b) perform a fluorescence microscopy analysis of e.g. the actin fibers of the cells, to complement the SEM assay.

The other method here described used a laser beam to produce grooves on the surface of a flat PET foil. It would be important that the authors showed the PET nanoripples produced by the laser beam without the presence of cells (as they did for the nanofibers in Figure 4). As nano-structuring can either promote or inhibit cell functions, nanoripples should be carefully characterized (by AFM for instance) to give readers a quantified indication of the nanostructure quality and period that promoted Schwann cells orientation. Optimum LIPSS formation should be identified. The LIPSS as a response to the laser parameters should be thoroughly explored. For instance, LIPSS in polymers can depend on the energy distribution within pulses, polarization direction, and wavelength as well as repetition rate, therefore influencing both the period and quality of the resulting nanostructures. If the authors are unable to thoroughly explore laser parameters to optimize the LIPSS formation, they should at least explain in the discussion section how they selected the current parameters and how their variation would be expected to affect the nanoripples formation.

Other issues that in our opinion should be addressed to improve the article:

- Schwann cells cultures (better subtitle) should include the cell density upon seeding on the coated biomaterials.
- The biological readout is a single one (visual analyses of SEM images) and the article would gain with other host-interaction tests, such as cell viability, proliferation and/or adhesion
- The Discussion is scarce and would gain with examples of other reported aligned nanofibers using different polymers and cues for neural cells, and by hypothesizing how could the biomaterials here presented be employed in in vivo strategies.

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Is the rationale for developing the new method (or application) clearly explained?

Partly

Is the description of the method technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details provided to allow replication of the method development and its use by others?

Yes

If any results are presented, are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions about the method and its performance adequately supported by the findings presented in the article?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Sandra I. Vieira - Neuroscience, neuroregeneration and neurodegeneration, in-vitro studies of nervous system, host-biomaterials interactions. Nathalie Barroca – manufacturing of platforms for bone and neural tissue repair; electromechanical couplings in biomaterials and tissues

We confirm that we have read this submission and believe that we have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however we have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 14 Aug 2024

Sebastian Lifka

We would like to thank the reviewer for the helpful comments and suggestions on our manuscript and it is with great pleasure that we upload a revised version. To improve the quality of our paper, we revised our manuscript according to the reviewers' suggestions for improvement. Below is our detailed response to the reviewers' comments.

Comment #1: *The Introduction section has some relevant reported data, but nothing on the biological problem that authors aim to tackle, which should not only be addressed in the Abstract (attention that PNI regeneration is not that ineffective – only in 'large defects'). To better contextualize the need for the here-developed biomaterials, authors should include a short characterization of the PNS regeneration process, including the role of Schwann cells in bands of Bungner, in the Introduction section. This is necessary to support the author's Conclusion that the alignment of Schwann cells may subsequently lead to better axonal regeneration.* In the peripheral nervous system of vertebrates, neurons are responsible for receiving and transmitting electrical and chemical signals and glial cells provide the necessary support and protection for neurons. Here, the most important glial cells are Schwann cells. They are responsible for the creation of myelin sheaths that protect and insulate neuronal axons. They are also essential and indispensable for axon regeneration in the event of injury. The peripheral axons regenerate in regeneration tracks (i.e., Bünger bands) formed by elongated Schwann cells. Small gaps can regenerate from alone while large gaps are considered to require the support of a nerve graft. But the currently proposed artificial nerve grafts have insufficient success rates, especially for large nerve gaps of several cm, and nerve autografts cause severe functional loss or risk of morbidity at the donor sites. A key factor here is the elongated orientation of the Schwann cells which is induced by stimuli from their surrounding either in the extra cellular matrix or in case of artificial implants by the supporting material. We have added these considerations in a new paragraph at the

beginning of the section Introduction with the new reference Manganas et al., 2022.

Comment #2: *As for the manufacturing technologies, the introduction should also contextualize better the current state of the art regarding the exploitation of electrospinning and LIPSS, to highlight their relevance for repairing strategies for the PNS. For instance, the direct laser patterning technique has been already used to fabricate nanoripples and dual-rough hierarchical micro/nano structures to control Schwann cells attachment and migration. [Refer ref 1]. Also, since nano-structuring is known for both boosting and inhibiting cell functions, this should be carefully explained in the introduction.*

We have added two new paragraphs in the section Introduction. i.e., the second and the third, with more details on the state of the art regarding the exploitation of electrospinning and LIPSS for nerve repair graft and control of cell growth, respectively. We refer here to the new references (Chen et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2018; Kriebel et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2020; Fosodeder et al., 2020; Muck et al., 2021; Maalouf et al., 2022), as well as the reference (Yiannakou et al., 2017), which was suggested by the reviewer.

Comment #3: *Regarding the cellular alignment assay, one thing noticed is that the nanofibers of Figure 6B augmentation do not seem aligned, and authors should present a more representative zoom-in.*

Thank you very much for bringing this to our attention. We have added two new SEM images which show the underlying nanofibers in more detail. Figure 6B now shows random oriented nanofibers under the cells and Figure 6D shows the aligned nanofibers under the cells. Additionally, we performed a directionality analysis of the nanofibers under the cells. The resulting histograms show a clear orientation of the nanofibers and can be found in the Zenodo repository as extended Data (Figure S2).

Comment #4: *Also, no control such as randomly aligned nanofibers, was here included for comparison purposes, and so the readers cannot visually certify the cell alignment effect. As this biomaterial is the core of this article, it would also be desirable to a) apply the same strategy as the one used in Figure 5 to have some quantitative data on cell alignment; b) perform a fluorescence microscopy analysis of e.g. the actin fibers of the cells, to complement the SEM assay.*

As already requested by Reviewer 1, we applied the same analysis methods as for the oriented nanofibers to the cells and included the resulting histograms in the manuscript. In addition, we performed fluorescence microscopy of cells on nanofibers (on flat cover glass surface, randomly oriented, and aligned) and on a flat cover glass as control as requested. For space reasons, these images are only available in the Zenodo repository as extended data (Figure S3). The reason why we originally only analyzed SEM images was because this is the gold standard for analyzing the directionality of fibers or cells. On the other hand, the underlying fibers are not visible in fluorescence microscopy and thus it cannot be verified and shown that the cells really spread in the fiber direction.

Comment #5: *The other method here described used a laser beam to produce grooves on the surface of a flat PET foil. It would be important that the authors showed the PET nanoripples produced by the laser beam without the presence of cells (as they did for the nanofibers in Figure 4).*

We replaced one zoom-in SEM image of Figure 7 with an even more zoomed-in SEM image of the nanoripples without cells.

Comment #6: *As nano-structuring can either promote or inhibit cell functions, nanoripples should be carefully characterized (by AFM for instance) to give readers a quantified indication of the nanostructure quality and period that promoted Schwann cells orientation.*

We absolutely agree with the reviewer. These nanoripples have already been characterized in our previous work (Buchberger et al., 2023 and Heitz et al., 2024) using optical methods and AFM. The typical spatial period is about 330 nm and the height is between 110 nm and 160 nm. We have described this in more detail in the manuscript and referred to the two papers mentioned.

Comment #7: *Optimum LIPSS formation should be identified. The LIPSS as a response to the laser parameters should be thoroughly explored. For instance, LIPSS in polymers can depend on the energy distribution within pulses, polarization direction, and wavelength as well as repetition rate, therefore influencing both the period and quality of the resulting nanostructures. If the authors are unable to thoroughly explore laser parameters to optimize the LIPSS formation, they should at least explain in the discussion section how they selected the current parameters and how their variation would be expected to affect the nanoripples formation.*

In our previous work, we have investigated (for other cell types) the parameter range within one can observe “surface-induced alignment” of the cells. Within this range we saw no qualitative difference of the alignment effect. Both methods presented here provide parallel features which correspond to surface-induced alignment regime and we show here for the first time that they can be used for the orientation of Schwann cells, in deed. However, we expect no strong qualitative effect of a variation the structure size (within this regime) on the alignment. We have added these considerations in a new paragraph at the end of the section Discussion with the new references Barb et al., 2014, Barb et al., 2015, and Peterbauer et al., 2010.

Comment #8: *Schwann cells cultures (better subtitle) should include the cell density upon seeding on the coated biomaterials.*

The cell density upon seeding was 25,000 cells per cm² resulting in a total number of approximately 65,000 cells per sample. We added this to the cell cultivation subsection in the manuscript.

Comment #9: *The biological readout is a single one (visual analyses of SEM images) and the article would gain with other host-interaction tests, such as cell viability, proliferation and/or adhesion.*

We can understand the reviewer's view, but we are currently still struggling with our methods to determine cell adhesion, as the samples used here are very flexible and therefore cannot be measured reliably with our methods. Furthermore, when determining viability and proliferation, we see the problem that our samples are structured and therefore have a significantly different surface size than a flat control sample, which in our opinion makes the evaluation difficult and not very meaningful. A single cell analysis might be possible, but it is difficult and extremely imprecise. As this article focuses on a method for directional growth of Schwann cells, we have refrained from determining additional parameters.

Comment #10: *The Discussion is scarce and would gain with examples of other reported aligned nanofibers using different polymers and cues for neural cells, and by hypothesizing how could the biomaterials here presented be employed in in vivo strategies.*

We see the point of the reviewer, but we think we have addressed it already in the description of the state of the art in the second paragraph of the section Introduction (see above).

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 08 June 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.18773.r40812>

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Harald Luksch

Technische Universität München, Weihenstephan, Germany

In their submission entitled “Oriented artificial nanofibers and laser induced periodic surface structures as substrates for Schwann cells alignment”, Lifka and colleagues describe a way of structuring surfaces for better orientation of biological cells. Such orientation might be helpful for oriented growth of neurons in, e.g, regeneration processes after injuries to the peripheral nervous system.

Lifka et al use two different methods for structuring the surface, namely the production of grooves with a laser beam, or the production of a nanofiber mat with electrospun polyamide nanofibers. For the latter process, a key feature of the spinning process was improved by using a fast rotating structured collector with a knurled surface. The woven nanofiber mat can be removed without damage or residual material attached to the collector. Both the mat and the laser-fabricated grooves were inspected with Scanning Electron Microscopy and showed well aligned fibers or grooves, respectively.

The authors then cultivated mouse Schwann cells from a cell line onto either substrate for a week, and analysed the orientation of the cells and their processes. From the images provided in the submission, a clear influence of the structure on the cellular orientation is evident. However, a quantitative assessment of cell orientation in both the control cultures and the cultures on structured surfaces would have been good, to clearly show the orientation and to quantify the effect of the given structure. After all, the parameters chosen for either structuring method might be suboptimal, and variations of the structures (i.e., deeper or wider grooves etc.) might lead to even better orientation control. The authors conclude that their production of mechanical nanofeatures is capable of influencing glial cells into an oriented growth, and thus may potentially aid axonal regeneration.

My impression is that this report is a valuable addition to manufacturing processes for structured surfaces for nerve regeneration. The method description is sound, the images illustrate the respective issues well, and the conclusions are well founded.

Is the rationale for developing the new method (or application) clearly explained?

Yes

Is the description of the method technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details provided to allow replication of the method development and its use by others?

Yes

If any results are presented, are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions about the method and its performance adequately supported by the findings presented in the article?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Neuroscience, in-vitro studies of nervous system, neurophysiology, neuroanatomy.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 14 Aug 2024

Sebastian Lifka

We would like to thank the reviewer for the helpful comments and suggestions on our manuscript and it is with great pleasure that we upload a revised version. To improve the quality of our paper, we revised our manuscript according to the reviewers' suggestions for improvement. Below is our detailed response to the reviewers' comments.

Comment #1: *From the images provided in the submission, a clear influence of the structure on the cellular orientation is evident. However, a quantitative assessment of cell orientation in both the control cultures and the cultures on structured surfaces would have been good, to clearly show the orientation and to quantify the effect of the given structure.*

Thank you very much for that valuable input, we added a figure (Figure 8) where we analyzed the directionality of the cells on the nanofibers (random oriented and aligned) and on the PET foils (flat and with nanoripples) using the same method as for the analysis of the aligned nanofibers. The resulting histograms show a clear orientation of the cells on aligned nanofibers and nano-structured PET foils.

Comment #2: *After all, the parameters chosen for either structuring method might be suboptimal, and variations of the structures (i.e., deeper or wider grooves etc.) might lead to even better orientation control.*

In our previous work, we have investigated (for other cell types) the parameter range within one can observe "surface-induced alignment" of the cells. Within this range we saw no qualitative difference of the alignment effect. Both methods presented here provide parallel features which correspond to surface-induced alignment regime and we show here for the

first time that they can be used for the orientation of Schwann cells, in deed. However, we expect no strong qualitative effect of a variation the structure size (within this regime) on the alignment. We have added these considerations in a new paragraph at the end of the section Discussion with the new references Barb et al., 2014, Barb et al., 2015, and Peterbauer et al., 2010.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.
